

Effects of the business model on dividend policy: Evidence from US banks

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Abstract: Using a large panel of US bank holding companies, we provide one of the first examinations on the relation between bank business model and dividend policy. We document consistent evidence of higher dividends for diversified banks. Private banks that engage in non-traditional banking activities tend to pay more dividends than public banks do. This positive effect is more pronounced for medium banks, following small banks. However, we do not observe any relation between business model and dividend payment for large banks. The effect of diversification on the dividend is mitigating during the crisis. Our evidence remains unchanged with alternative measures as well as econometric approaches. Our study is of interest to regulators and policymakers who are concerns about the bank business model.

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1. Introduction

Banks are inherently more opaque than non-financial firms and are considered as black boxes from the perspectives of regulators (Morgan, 2002; Tran & Ashraf, 2018). During the 1970s, regulators start to liberalize the banking industry, allowing banks to expand into highly volatile and complex non-traditional banking activities previously prohibited (Tran Hassan, & Houston, 2019a). This deregulation together with financial innovation and technological progress adds even greater complexity to the balance sheets of banks (Financial Crisis Inquiry Commission, 2011), strengthening the asymmetric information problems in diversified banks.

Dividend policy is considered as a potential channel to mitigate the agency problems and asymmetric information, since dividend might be used to monitor managers, and is a costly signal to convey information to less informed outsiders (Tran & Ashraf, 2018). Whereas there exists a large literature examining bank business model, however, most of these studies concentrate to the association between the organizational form and the risk-taking and performance of banks (see e.g. Stiroh, 2004; Stiroh & Rumble, 2006; DeYoung & Torna, 2013; Holod & Peek, 2010; Holod & Torna, 2018; Tran et al., 2019a) among others). In the aftermath of the global financial crisis, casino-style gambling on Wall Street is blamed as one of the critical reasons for the severity of the crisis. Given the important role of banks for the real sectors, the lack of research on the activity strategies determinants of bank dividend policy is surprising and potentially consequential.

In this study, our objective is to provide one of the first empirical examinations on whether the dividend policy varies across banks with a different business model. Do focused banks have different dividend policies compared with diversified banks?

Our main hypothesis relies on the coinsurance effect arising from diversification. It is generally stated that under the perspective of modern portfolio theory, the combination of different activities reduces the variance of the returns since they are not perfectly correlated, resulting in a coinsurance effect, diversification gains and a more stable revenue stream (DeYoung & Roland, 2001; Tran, 2019a), reducing the total risk and the probability of failure of diversified banks (Brewer, 1989; Saunders & Cornett, 2008). Indeed, different activities might coinsurance each other in their future cash-flows, and investment opportunities, reducing the need for precautionary savings (Jordan, Liu, & Wu, 2018). Consequently, diversified banks might need to hold less liquidity and liquid assets, which in turn allow them to pay out more dividend.

Furthermore, the information retrieved from each activity can be profitably re-used for other functions of diversified banks (Diamond, 1984). For example, diversified banks can retrieve borrower's information, and re-use it for non-traditional banking activities such as securities underwriting (Yasuda, 2005; Bharath, Dahiya, Saunders, & Srinivasan, 2007). Or, non-traditional banking activities might help diversified banks to ease their loan-making decisions, resulting in better credit risk management. Therefore, we suggest that diversified banks might pay more dividends than other banks since they are financially stronger.

Prior literature documents the concern of intensified agency problems at diversified banks (Tran, 2019a), leading to discretionary decisions to undertake value-decreasing investments (Berger & Ofek, 1995). Dividend policy is considered as a potential channel to mitigate the agency problems and asymmetric information, since dividend might be used to monitor managers, and is a costly signal to convey information to less informed outsiders (Tran & Ashraf, 2018). Then, we suppose that diversified banks tend to pay more dividends to mitigate their agency problem with shareholders.

In this paper, we shed light on the association between diversification and bank dividend policy using a large sample of US bank holding companies (BHC) from 2000:Q1 to 2017:Q4. Controlling for the effects of different bank characteristics and bank- and time-fixed effects, our empirical analysis provides consistent evidence on higher dividend payments for diversified banks. The evidence is economically significant. For example, our baseline model indicates that one standard deviation increase of NII would lead to an increase in a dividend payment of 3.7%. Our main finding remains unchanged with alternative sub-samples and measures. This evidence is consistent with the findings of Jordan, Liu, & Wu (2018) who study the relation of dividend policy and organizational form of non-financial firms.

We also document a variation of the effect of diversification on bank dividend policy across bank size. Diversification is related to higher dividends for small and medium banks, but not for large banks. The magnitude of the coefficient on NII is largest with medium banks sample, suggesting medium banks might benefit more from diversification gains, and might pay a higher dividend. For large banks samples, there is no evidence of the association between diversification and dividend. Potential explanations are as follows.

Larger banks are more likely to exploit from non-traditional activities for a long time, reach their saturated level of diversification, and won't gain any benefits from marginal increases of diversification but potentially greater agency problems (Tran, 2019b). Despite having more rooms to gain from diversification, small banks may lack experiences in new and more complex non-traditional activities, then reducing their operating stability and dividend payout (Tran et al., 2019a).

We investigate whether diversification affects differently dividend policy during the crisis. The results suggest that diversified banks pay fewer dividends during the crisis than normal times. This evidence to the same extent supports the finding of Tran (2019b) who suggests that banks that move toward non-traditional activities create more liquidity during the crisis time.

We address the endogeneity concerns since the decision to diversify is a deliberate decision by bank managers. They may choose to diversify when they get more benefits than the costs of diversification (Campa & Kedia, 2002). We use the propensity score matching and the Heckman two-step model. In all specifications, our findings remain quantitatively similar to our main evidence.

Our study contributes to the literature. To the best of our limited knowledge, our study provides the first investigation of the impacts of functional diversification on the dividend policy within the US banking industry. There exist several studies explaining the association between dividend policy and business model of non-financial firms. Jordan, Liu, & Wu (2018) show that conglomerates pay out more than pure plays in dividend payment.

Duchin (2010) suggests that conglomerates hold less cash than pure plays. Our study, by focusing on one of the most regulated banking industries, and using a comprehensive sample with a long duration would make our findings stronger, more robust, and not biased by sample selection. We contribute to the literature of dividend policy by showing evidence of higher payout for diversified banks. And this positive effect varies across bank size.

The next section describes the data and variables. Section 3 reports the main results and alternative tests. We provide additional tests in Section 4. Section 5 concludes the study.

2. Data, and variables

The Federal Reserve provides quarterly Y-9C regulatory reports filed by bank holding companies (BHC) with assets of \$150 million and over. Our raw data cover the period 2000:Q1 to 2017:Q4. We remove any bank-quarter observations with missing or incomplete financial data on accounting variables in the main regression model. All financial ratios are winsorized at a 1% level on the top and bottom of their distribution to mitigate the effects of outliers.

Following prior literature such as Stiroh & Rumble (2006), De Jonghe, Diepstraten, & Schepens (2015), Tran, Hassan, & Houston (2019b), we capture the activity strategies of banks using bank income structure, which is measured as the ratio of non-interest income over the net operating income (NII). We also use alternative measures and still reach similar evidence. We use the ratio of dividends to total equity capital (DPO) as a proxy for dividend policy.

To mitigate a potential omitted variable bias, we control for various bank-specific variables. We include bank size (SIZE), capital ratio (CAPITAL), bank performance (EARNINGS), an indicator of losses (DUMMY_LOSS), assets growth (GROWTH). See Table 1 for definitions, and Table 2 for summary descriptive. Table 2 reports summary statistics and correlation for the main sample of U.S. commercial banks used in the analysis. All financial variables are winsorized at 1% and 99% levels.

TABLE 1. VARIABLES DEFINITIONS

VARIABLES	DEFINITIONS
<i>Dependent variables</i>	
DPO	The ratio of dividends over the total equity capital
<i>Control variables</i>	
NII	Non-interest incomes over the net operating incomes
NII_QUARTILE	In each quarter, we rank NII variable into quartiles and create a variable called NII_QUARTILE, which takes a value ranging from 1 (low) to 4 (high)
LOAN	Loans over gross total assets
TRADING	Including trading revenues, interest income from trading assets and the realized gains or losses from the held-to-maturity and available-for-sale securities
HHI	$HHI = 1 - [(NII)^2 + (NIM)^2]$
SIZE	The natural logarithm of gross total assets
CAPITAL	Book value of equity over gross total assets
EARNINGS	Income before taxes, provisions recognized in income over gross total assets
GROWTH	The growth rate of gross total assets
NII_AVG	Average of NII of all other banks
BFE	Bank fixed effects
TFE	Time fixed effects, represented by dummies for each quarter of the sample period.

TABLE 2. SUMMARY STATISTICS

PANEL A: SUMMARY STATISTICS					
	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
LC	34,941	0.456	0.174	(0.027)	0.899
NII	34,309	0.235	0.131	0.000	0.814
SIZE	34,941	13.934	1.237	12.089	19.109
CAP	34,941	0.090	0.028	0.019	0.220
EARNINGS	34,941	0.015	0.009	(0.020)	0.051
GROWTH	34,941	0.016	0.042	(0.085)	0.229
NPL	34,941	0.018	0.022	-	0.118
ZSCORE	34,941	43.508	37.935	0.465	197.907
SD(EARNINGS)	34,941	0.005	0.007	0.001	0.047

PANEL B: CORRELATION									
	LC	NII	SIZE	CAP	EARNINGS	GROWTH	NPL	ZSCORE	SD(EARNINGS)
LC	1.000								
NII	-0.1055***	1.000							
SIZE	0.1380***	0.3728***	1.000						
CAP	-0.1915***	0.0762***	0.0550***	1.000					
EARNINGS	0.1299***	0.1514***	0.1142***	0.3575***	1.000				
GROWTH	0.1214***	0.0163***	0.0436***	-0.0280***	0.1515***	1.000			
NPL	-0.1157***	-0.0106**	0.0617***	-0.1311***	-0.3612***	-0.2236***	1.000		
ZSCORE	-0.0200***	-0.0615***	0.0461***	0.2277***	0.2575***	0.1078***	-0.3868***	1.000	
SD(EARNINGS)	-0.0924***	0.1586***	0.1086***	0.0334***	-0.1770***	-0.1157***	0.3532***	-0.4209***	1.000

3. Do activity strategies affect the bank's dividend policy?

3.1. Main results

We conduct multivariate analysis to examine how activity strategies might affect bank's dividend policy after controlling other control variables. Our baseline model is as follows:

$$DPO_{it} = \alpha_i + NII_{it-1} + Z_{it-1} + \mu_i + \theta_t + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

where DPO_{it} is the proxy for the dividend policy of bank i at time t . Our variable of interest is NII, which is the ratio of non-interest incomes over the net operating incomes. Z_{it} is the vector of control variables described above. In all of our specifications, we lag all independent variables by 1 period of time to mitigate the simultaneity and endogeneity problems. We include bank fixed-effects, μ_i , which is motivated by the fact that differences in bank dividend policy are partly related to unobservable but time-invariant characteristics of banks such as corporate culture, bank management, etc. Time-fixed effects, θ_t , are also included to control for time effects which can affect the dividend policy of banks. ε_{it} is the error term. Since DPO is likely to be correlated within a bank over time, standard errors used to assess significance are corrected for heteroscedasticity and bank-level clustering.

TABLE 3. BASELINE MULTIVARIATE ANALYSIS

	Baseline model	Additional variables	Balanced panel data	Excluding M&A	Excluding crisis periods	Only diversified banks	Only focused banks	Private	Public	Logit
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)
<i>NII</i>	0.283*** (0.078)	0.260*** (0.077)	0.328** (0.142)	0.279*** (0.079)	0.290*** (0.078)	0.265*** (0.084)	1.323* (0.734)	0.326*** (0.097)	0.227* (0.118)	0.528* (0.300)
<i>SIZE</i>	0.067** (0.030)	0.064** (0.029)	0.175*** (0.053)	0.077** (0.030)	0.038 (0.030)	0.068** (0.031)	0.247** (0.110)	0.037 (0.041)	0.117*** (0.045)	0.272*** (0.040)
<i>CAPITAL</i>	2.840*** (0.411)	2.551*** (0.402)	1.459 (0.915)	2.960*** (0.423)	2.520*** (0.382)	2.834*** (0.423)	3.376** (1.632)	4.043*** (0.639)	1.632*** (0.580)	1.278 (1.214)
<i>EARNINGS</i>	-4.572*** (0.858)	-3.987*** (0.856)	-5.733*** (1.637)	-4.681*** (0.867)	-2.353*** (0.885)	-4.776*** (0.893)	-3.070 (3.311)	-3.304*** (1.098)	-5.832*** (1.356)	36.972*** (4.475)
<i>GROWTH</i>	-0.143* (0.076)	-0.189** (0.076)	0.052 (0.146)	-0.142* (0.076)	-0.090 (0.073)	-0.105 (0.077)	-0.678** (0.338)	-0.129 (0.109)	-0.166* (0.097)	-2.916*** (0.332)
<i>DUMMY_LOSS</i>	0.060** (0.029)	0.061** (0.029)	-0.040 (0.054)	0.058** (0.029)	0.087*** (0.031)	0.062** (0.030)	0.066 (0.150)	0.062* (0.037)	0.048 (0.046)	-1.177*** (0.073)
Constant	-0.703* (0.406)	-0.203 (0.413)	-2.114*** (0.745)	-0.842** (0.416)	-0.310 (0.411)	-0.711* (0.423)	-3.166** (1.518)	-0.391 (0.560)	-1.377** (0.627)	-4.045*** (0.516)
Observations	38,980	38,857	8,163	38,544	34,991	35,973	3,007	24,764	14,216	67,887
R-squared	0.048	0.056	0.062	0.049	0.028	0.048	0.082	0.045	0.083	0.080
Number of rssid9001	2,290	2,290	203	2,286	2,274	2,175	576	1,720	634	
BFE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
QFE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Note: This table reports regression estimates of the relation between NII and DPO. All financial variables are winsorized at the 1% and 99% levels. ***, **, * indicate significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% level respectively. Standard errors are clustered at the bank level. The numbers in parentheses are t-statistics.

Table 3 reports the main results. Model (1) reports our baseline model. We include additional variables in Model (2). In both models, the coefficients on NII are positive and

statistically significant at the 1% level, suggesting that banks that move towards non-interest income generating activities increase their dividend payout. Regarding the economic magnitude of this effect, one standard deviation increase of NII, holding all other equal, increases DPO of 0.037 (i.e. the coefficient on NII, 0.283, times the standard deviation of NII, 0.129). With a mean of 0.542 and a standard deviation of 0.560, this increase of DPO is equivalent to 6.736% of the average DPO. This evidence supports the findings of Jordan, Liu, & Wu (2018) and is consistent with Duchin (2010).

In Model (3), we use the balanced panel data that allow us to mitigate the effects of M&A activities and bank defaults on our investigation, but at the price of over-representing "successful" banks. In Model (4), we exclude M&A banks (banks with a large change in assets over periods, we use a threshold of 20% of assets change over quarter).^{*} The coefficients of NII remain positive and statistically significant at the 1% level for all specifications.

In Model (6) and (7), we perform our baseline model with samples containing only diversified and focused banks, respectively. We classify banks as diversified and focused banks following Laeven & Levine (2007). More specifically, the bank is considered a diversified bank if its share of non-interest income is between [0.10; 0.90], otherwise it is considered as a focused bank. We observe that the coefficient on NII is much larger in focused banks sample than in diversified banks sample (1.323 versus 0.265). This evidence suggests that focused banks that increase the share of non-interest income will benefit more from the coinsurance effect, then increase more their payout ratio.

In Model (8) and (9), we perform our baseline model with samples containing only private and public banks, respectively, since the separation of control from ownership might affect the bank decisions (Iran et al., 2019a, 2019b), then their dividend policy (Short, Zhang, & Keasey, 2002; Mancinelli & Ozkan, 2006). We observe that the effect of NII on DPO is more pronounced with the sample of private banks than in public banks.

In Model (10), we perform a logistic regression. The dependent variable is the dummy variable, equals to 1 if the bank pays dividends, and 0 otherwise. We document that diversified banks are more likely than other banks to pay dividends. In unreported tests, we use alternative sub-samples such as excluding the top largest banks (top 10th percentile of bank assets, and TBTF banks). Again, we observe that diversified banks still experience a higher dividend payout ratio than other banks.

Regardless of the control variables (Model 1), we observe that large and well-capitalized banks are more likely to pay more dividends. Highly profitable and high growth-opportunities banks pay fewer dividends than other banks. The evidence also shows that banks experiencing losses pay a higher dividend than other banks.

In brief, our findings suggest diversified banks are more likely to pay dividends, and pay more dividends than other banks. The results are robust with alternative sub-samples.

3.2. The effect of diversification on dividend across bank size

Table 4 reports the results of our baseline model for a different size range of banks: (i) small banks with assets up to \$1 billion, (ii) medium banks with assets between \$1 billion and \$5 billion, and (iii) large banks with assets over \$5 billion.

^{*} We also use other threshold, and find similar findings.

TABLE 4. THE EFFECT OF DIVERSIFICATION ON LIQUIDITY CREATION FOR A DIFFERENT SIZE RANGE

	Small (1)	Medium (2)	Large (3)
<i>NII</i>	0.249** (0.114)	0.355*** (0.136)	0.154 (0.167)
<i>SIZE</i>	0.019 (0.052)	0.089 (0.059)	0.270*** (0.060)
<i>CAPITAL</i>	4.770*** (0.635)	1.999*** (0.744)	1.348 (0.960)
<i>EARNINGS</i>	-5.527*** (1.227)	-3.771*** (1.428)	-3.940* (2.180)
<i>GROWTH</i>	-0.075 (0.102)	-0.138 (0.137)	-0.265 (0.167)
<i>DUMMY_LOSS</i>	0.096** (0.041)	-0.002 (0.050)	0.013 (0.065)
Constant	-0.181 (0.687)	-1.017 (0.834)	-4.092*** (0.991)
Observations	23,808	10,076	5,096
R-squared	0.044	0.068	0.097
Number of rssd9001	1,807	587	447
BFE	Yes	Yes	Yes
QFE	Yes	Yes	Yes

Note: This table reports regression estimates of the relation between NII and DPO across bank size. All financial variables are winsorized at the 1% and 99% levels. ***, **, * indicate significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% level respectively. Standard errors are clustered at the bank level. The numbers in parentheses are t-statistics.

The results in all three models (1)-(3) indicate that diversification is related to a higher dividend for small and medium banks, but not for large banks. The magnitude of the coefficient on NII is largest with medium banks sample, suggesting medium banks might benefit more from diversification gains, and might pay a higher dividend. For large banks samples, there is no evidence of the association between diversification and dividend. Potential explanations are as follows. Larger banks are more likely to exploit from non-traditional activities for a long time, reach their saturated level of diversification, and won't gain any benefits from marginal increases of diversification but potentially greater agency problems (Tran, 2019b). Despite having more rooms to gain from diversification, small banks may lack experiences in new and more complex non-traditional activities, then reducing their operating stability and dividend payout (Tran et al., 2019b).

In sum, we document a variation of the effect of diversification on dividend payout across bank size. The positive effect of the shifting toward non-interest income-generating activities on dividend payout is strongest for medium banks, following by small diversified banks. Large banks experience no effect of diversification on dividend payout.

3.3. Effects of diversification on dividend during the crisis

We examine whether the association between NII and DPO varies during the global financial crisis. The crisis period is from 2007:Q3 - 2009:Q2 following Acharya & Mora (2015). We re-run our baseline model by adding the crisis dummy and the interaction of the crisis dummy with NII (NII*CRISIS). Our focus is the coefficient of the interaction term, which measures how the crisis affects the association between diversification and dividend payment. The results are reported in Table 5.

TABLE 5. THE EFFECTS OF THE CRISIS

	(1)
<i>NII</i>	0.305*** (0.078)
<i>NII * CRISIS</i>	-0.237** (0.112)
<i>CRISIS</i>	0.401*** (0.058)
<i>SIZE</i>	0.066** (0.030)
<i>CAPITAL</i>	2.845*** (0.411)
<i>EARNINGS</i>	-4.517*** (0.857)
<i>GROWTH</i>	-0.139* (0.076)
<i>DUMMY_LOSS</i>	0.061** (0.029)
Constant	-0.695* (0.406)
Observations	38,980
R-squared	0.048
Number of rssid9001	2,290
BFE	Yes
QFE	Yes

Note: This table reports regression estimates of the relation between NII and DPO during the crisis time. All financial variables are winsorized at the 1% and 99% levels. ***, **, * indicate significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% level respectively. Standard errors are clustered at the bank level. The numbers in parentheses are t-statistics.

The results suggest that diversified banks pay fewer dividends during the crisis than normal times as indicated by the negative and statistically significant coefficient on *NII*CRISIS*. This evidence to the same extent supports the finding of Tran (2019b) who suggests that banks that move toward non-traditional activities create more liquidity during the crisis time.

4. Robustness checks

4.1. Alternative measures of diversification

In Table 6, we re-conduct our baseline model with alternative measures of bank diversification. In Model (1), we first rank NII variable into quartiles and create a variable called *NII_QUARTILE*, which takes a value ranging from 1 (low) to 4 (high). This approach generates greater variation in the distribution of the extent of diversification.

TABLE 6. ALTERNATIVE MEASURES OF DIVERSIFICATION

	NII_QUARTILE (1)	HHI (2)	Trading (3)	Loan (4)
<i>NII</i>	0.018*** (0.005)	0.283*** (0.074)	0.157** (0.069)	-0.231*** (0.089)
<i>SIZE</i>	0.067** (0.030)	0.069** (0.030)	0.055* (0.029)	0.053* (0.029)
<i>CAPITAL</i>	2.856*** (0.410)	2.852*** (0.412)	2.818*** (0.411)	2.813*** (0.409)
<i>EARNINGS</i>	-4.121*** (0.841)	-4.232*** (0.842)	-3.804*** (0.836)	-3.240*** (0.828)
<i>GROWTH</i>	-0.137* (0.075)	-0.137* (0.076)	-0.124* (0.075)	-0.149** (0.075)
<i>DUMMY_LOSS</i>	0.064** (0.029)	0.064** (0.029)	0.061** (0.029)	0.064** (0.029)
Constant	-0.705* (0.411)	-0.763* (0.415)	-0.490 (0.399)	-0.320 (0.398)
Observations	38,980	38,808	39,131	39,161
R-squared	0.048	0.048	0.047	0.048
Number of rssid9001	2,290	2,288	2,291	2,292
BFE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
QFE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Note: This table reports regression estimates of the relation between NII and DPO using alternative measures of diversification. All financial variables are winsorized at the 1% and 99% levels. ***, **, * indicate significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% level respectively. Standard errors are clustered at the bank level. The numbers in parentheses are t-statistics.

Following Stiroh & Rumble (2006), Tran et al. (2019b), in Model (2), we use an adjusted Herfindahl-Hirschman index to measure diversification (*HHI*), which accounts for variations in the breakdown of net operating income (*NOI*) into two main categories: net interest income (*NIM*) and noninterest income (*NII*). We document that a higher degree of diversification leads to an increase in dividend payment.

$$HHI = 1 - [(NIM)^2 + (NII)^2] \quad (2)$$

We next focus on the most controversial type of non-interest income, i.e. the trading incomes in Model (3). We compute the trading incomes following Gandhi, Kiefer, & Plazzi (2016) that suggest totalizing the trading revenues, interest income from trading assets, and the realized gains or losses from the held-to-maturity and available-for-sale securities. Using this measure allows us to mitigate the concern that non-interest incomes may include incomes derived from traditional activities.

We use the ratio of the loan over the total assets as the proxy of bank functional diversification (*LOAN*) in Model (4). In contrary with other measures, this measure is interpreted as an inverse diversification measure, since a higher value of loan ratio means that banks focus more on traditional banking activities.

The results shown in Models (3)-(4) confirm earlier findings, suggesting that a move toward non-traditional activities would make banks pay a higher dividend

4.2. Endogeneity concerns

Our investigation may be subject to reverse causality or endogeneity among variables. The specification in our baseline model is based on the assumption that a bank's decision to diversify is exogenous. However, diversification is not random, but is a deliberate decision made by bank managers, hence the same bank-level characteristics that drive the decision to diversify could also affect the dividend decisions of banks (Tran, 2019b). A failure to control for factors that drive banks to diversify leads to biased econometric results that inappropriately attribute the diversification costs and benefits to diversification per se rather than to the underlying traits that guide banks to diversify (Campa & Kedia, 2002).

TABLE 7. ENDOGENEITY CONCERNS

	PSM				Heckman selection	
	W/o replacement	N=1	N=2	N=3	1rst stage	2nd stage
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
NII	0.446** (0.209)	4.766*** (1.366)	1.784** (0.704)	1.018** (0.478)		0.271*** (0.084)
SIZE	0.054 (0.087)	-3.439*** (0.665)	0.163 (0.247)	-0.002 (0.158)	0.144*** (0.020)	0.068** (0.029)
CAPITAL	3.450*** (1.059)	0.808 (9.581)	5.358*** (2.032)	3.842** (1.659)	-1.449* (0.750)	2.830*** (0.423)
EARNINGS	-0.739 (2.233)	-2.958 (10.942)	-3.492 (6.730)	3.123 (4.600)	-1.599 (2.533)	-4.561*** (0.884)
GROWTH	-0.241 (0.212)	2.936 (2.211)	0.150 (0.561)	0.448 (0.624)	-1.350*** (0.236)	-0.150* (0.078)
DUMMY_LOSS	0.088 (0.073)	0.444** (0.206)	0.123 (0.160)	0.257 (0.162)	-0.484*** (0.049)	0.052* (0.030)
NIII AVERAGE					5.660*** (0.526)	
IMR						0.004*** (0.000)
Constant	-0.712 (1.169)	44.420*** (8.998)	-2.652 (3.230)	-0.184 (2.103)	-5.449*** (0.571)	-0.608 (0.406)
Observations	6239	302	827	1,326	69,050	37,310
R-squared	0.066	0.907	0.237	0.125	0.129	0.048
Number of rssid9001	1,378	302	528	744	2934	2,237
BFE	Yes	249	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
QFE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Note: The table reports regression estimates of the relation between NII and DPO. All financial variables are winsorized at the 1% and 99% levels. ***, **, * indicate significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% level respectively. Standard errors are clustered at the bank level. The numbers in parentheses are t-statistics.

Thus, we complement our OLS estimation with different approaches: the Heckman selection model, and the propensity score matching. These procedures should control for any selection bias that could be present in the above estimation. The results are tabulated in Table 7.

We first employ the propensity score matching (PSM) system developed by Rosenbaum & Rubin (1983) and extended by Heckman, Ichimura, & Todd (1997). To conduct propensity score matching (PSM), we separate the full sample into two groups: diversified (treated) and focused (untreated) banks. Following Laeven & Levine (2007), we classify

banks into two separate groups: (i) Banks with a share of net interest income between 10% and 90% are classified as diversified banks, whereas (ii) banks with share of net interest income either below 10% or above 90% are classified as focused (or specialized) banks. We measure the propensity of undergoing treatment (i.e. the probability of diversification) by using a logit model for both treated and untreated samples. Our dependent variable in this logit model is a binary variable which equals 1 if the bank is classified as a diversified bank, and equals zero otherwise. The logit model is similar to the one in the first stage of the Heckman selection model described below. We match each diversified bank with one focused bank sharing similar characteristics as reflected in their propensity scores. We retain only untreated observations whose propensity scores fall inside the interval defined for the treated group. We impose a tolerance level of 0.5% on the maximum propensity score distance allowed (caliper), to minimize the risk of bad matches. We use one-to-one matching without replacement, which requires each focused bank to be used exactly one time (Model 1). We also use one-to-one matching with replacement, which allows each focused (untreated) bank to be used more than once (Model 2). We then use nearest-neighbor matching (oversampling) with $N=2$ and $N=3$, which matches each treated bank with the two and three untreated banks that have the closest propensity score, respectively (Models (3) and (4), respectively). In all matched samples, we continue to find similar findings.

The matching estimator presented above mitigates the selection bias. However, there may be unobservable factors that explain decisions to diversify. We use the Heckman two-step approach to eliminate bias due to unobservable variables. We first model the selection of diversification by using the logit selection model and then obtain the inverse Mills ratio (IMR) - the omitted variable in Equation (1). Following Laeven & Levine (2007), we use the average non-interest income of other banks as an instrument variable. We then estimate the logit diversification-choice model and calculate IMR. The IMR is the conditional expectation of the model selection error term, given the banks' observable characteristics and decision to diversify. In the second stage, we re-estimate Equation (1) by including IMR as an additional control variable to correct for potential self-selection biases. Models (5)-(6) report the maximum likelihood estimates of the logit diversification-choice, and our baseline model augmented by IMR. Consistent with our core findings, we still document a positive and significant coefficient of NII.

In brief, whether estimating a Heckman selection model, employing propensity-scores matching, our findings remain unchanged, diversification per se increases bank dividend.

5. Conclusions

We provide one of the first examinations of the impacts of functional diversification on bank dividend policy using a large sample of US banks during the period of 2000:Q1 to 2017:Q4. Our baseline model has demonstrated that banks with an increased share of non-interest incomes increase their dividend payment. When performing our analysis across bank size, we have observed that medium banks that engage in non-interest income generating activities pay the most their dividends, following by small diversified banks. We do not observe any relation between diversification and dividend payment for large banks. Finally, we document that banks decrease their dividend payments during the crisis, partially due to the increased precautionary behaviors. We believe our results are of interest to policymakers in the times of restructuring the banking system after the global financial crisis. For further research, we plan to provide further details on the positive

effects of diversification on bank dividend policy, whether it is related to agency problems as documented in prior literature (Acharya, Le, & Shin, 2016).

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